

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Synthesis of Some New 1-(2-Thienyl)-3-(Substituted Phenyl)-2-Propen-1-ones of Antimicrobial Importance

S. C. Kushwaha*

For the last one decade the synthesis of compounds of the type Ph-CH=CH-R and Ph-CH=CH-CO-R, where R is a heterocyclic nucleus, have gained momentum due to their biological importance. Buu-Hoi¹ synthesized heterocyclic analogues of the above type and their functional thioderivatives which were found to possess strong tuberculostatic and fungistatic properties. During the same year Daniel² *et al* also reported the ability of the hydroxy-analogue to inhibit the activity of the enzyme dihydroxyphenylalanine decarboxylase. Further, it has been reported by Clark³ that the compounds in which R is a phenyl nucleus, the antimicrobial activity was influenced by the alteration of substituents in the phenyl nucleus.

In the light of the above properties, our extensive search⁴⁻⁷ for potential antifungal and antibacterial compounds was encouraged in this direction, and we were tempted to synthesize the thienyl analogues of the above type. The compounds were prepared by the so-called "cold alkaline condensation" of 2-acetothienone with *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes, *p*-methoxybenzaldehydes, *m*-, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes, *m*-, *p*-chlorobenzaldehydes, 3 : 4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde, *o*-vanillin, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and benzaldehyde. These compounds have been tested again against *B. subtilis* and *C. albicans* by the two-fold serial dilution method. The compound which has no substituent in the benzene nucleus has been found to be extremely active against fungus (Table II).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Acetothienone⁸. This compound was synthesized by the action of acetic anhydride (1 mole, 95%) on thiophene (2 moles) in the presence of phosphoric acid (6 ml, 85%). The reaction mixture, after completion of the reaction, was washed successively with water and 5% sodium bicarbonate and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate.

*Present address : Department of Physiological Chemistry, University of Wisconsin, Madison Wisconsin 53706, U.S.A.,

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The unchanged thiophene was removed by distillation under atmospheric conditions and the residue was then distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction, boiling between 89-90°/10mm, was our desired product (2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative, m.p. -245.5°).

TABLE I

Analytical data of 1-(2-Thienyl)-3-(Substituted Phenyl)-2-Propen-1-ones and their 2:4-Dinitrophenyl Hydrazones

Substituents	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	%Found		%Calculated		D. N. P.'S		M.P. °C
				C	H	C	H	%N Found	Cal.	
No substituent	81	71	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₈	72.65	4.85	72.80	4.62	14.0	14.2	246
2-nitro-	136	38	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ NS	60.0	3.60	60.23	3.47	—	—	—
3-nitro-	151	50	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ NS	60.1	3.65	60.23	3.47	—	—	—
3-chloro-	74	62	C ₁₃ H ₉ OCIS	62.49	3.85	62.77	3.62	—	—	—
4-chloro-	134	88	C ₁₃ H ₉ OCIS	62.56	3.70	62.77	3.62	12.9	13.0	233
3-hydroxy-	145	64	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ S	67.58	4.50	67.82	4.34	13.5	13.7	235
4-hydroxy-	180	48	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ S	67.95	4.15	67.82	4.34	13.4	13.7	248
3-methyl-	63	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ OS	73.41	5.00	73.68	5.26	13.5	13.7	200
4-methyl-	115	83	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ OS	73.70	5.45	73.68	5.26	—	—	—
4-methoxy-	86	87	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ S	68.62	5.13	68.85	4.91	13.1	13.2	183
3:4-methylene- dioxy	132	90	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ S	65.30	4.10	65.10	3.87	12.5	12.8	236
2-hydroxy-3- methoxy	148	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ S	64.60	4.45	64.61	4.61	—	—	—
4-dimethylamino	114	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ONS	69.79	5.53	70.04	5.83	15.8	16.0	185

General Procedure of Preparation. To a cold solution of 2-acetothienone (0.01 mole) and arylaldehyde (0.01 mole) in aldehyde-free ethanol (25 ml), was added a strong solution of potassium hydroxide (3.5 g in 5 ml of water), with constant shaking, at 20° and left at that temperature for 1 hr. However, in the case of ortho, metanitrobenzaldehydes, 10 ml of 10% potassium hydroxide solution was used as a condensing agent. It was then neutralized with 5% hydrochloric acid. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water, and then crystallized with suitable solvents.

TABLE II

Antimicrobial activity of 1-(2-Thienyl)-3-(Substituted phenyl)-2-propen-1-ones

Sl. No.	Substituents	Test organism	
		<i>B. subtilis</i> μg/ml	<i>C. albicans</i> μg/ml
1.	4-Chloro-	< 100	> 100
2.	4-Dimethylamino-	< 100	> 100
3.	3:4-Methylenedioxy-	< 100	> 100
4.	No substituent ^a	< 100	6.25
5.	4-Methyl-	< 100	> 100
6.	4-Methoxy- ^a	< 100	> 100
7.	3-Nitro-	< 100	> 100
8.	2-Nitro-	< 100	> 100
9.	3-Hydroxy- ^b	< 100	> 100
10.	4-Hydroxy-	< 100	> 100

^aB. A. Honson, *Bull. Soc., Chim.* (Belges), 1958, **67**, 712.

^bDaniel H. Deutsch, and Eugene N. Garcia, U. S. 2754, 299, July 10, 1956.

These compounds were not tested against fungus and other microbes by the above authors.

Method of Testing. The compounds of this series were tested for their antifungal and antibacterial activities by two-fold serial dilution method. For fungi the testings were done in modified Sabouroud's broth (incubation temp. $28 \pm 1^\circ$) and antibacterial in nutrients broth (incubation temp. 37°). Inoculum for these were prepared from 24 hours old stationary cultures and growth inhibitions were observed after 20 hrs. Results are recorded in Table II.

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H. B. TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE,
KANPUR,
INDIA.

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